

STATE REGULATION AND ANALYSIS OF TOURIST SERVICES MARKET

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Abstract. *The article reveals the role and importance of state regulation of the market of tourist services on the basis of scientific and theoretical analysis of the concept of “basic conditions structure - behavior – result”.*

Keywords: *market of tourist services, system of state regulation, the concept of “basic conditions - structure - behavior – result”.*

Introduction. The tourism network is a huge socio-economic system operating within the national economy. Like any system, its individual elements, interactions between them are coordinated through the regulatory levers of the market economy. However, no matter how improved and perfect the tourist services market is, it cannot fully solve socio-economic problems such as training personnel for the tourism network, preservation and protection of historical and cultural heritage, environmental protection, ensuring the safety of tourists, and modernization of the transport system. These shortcomings in the market of tourist services can be eliminated by effective regulation by the state.

The regulation of the economy by the state means the activity of the state on the organization of the social production process aimed at achieving a general economic balance that ensures more effective use of limited production resources to increase the level of meeting the needs of members of society.

Revealing the content and essence of the market of tourist services and determining the place of regulation of its development by the state is of theoretical and practical importance and is aimed at increasing the efficiency of social production. In the history of economic thought, the question of the role of the state in the economy was considered on a scientific basis.

Various branch markets and organizations operating in the national economy are objects of state regulation. They are regulated by regulatory entities, that is, various state authorities, regional and local self-government bodies, using various means and methods.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process

Analysis and results. The market operating in the conditions of a market economy is primarily regulated by its levers. Based on this, fundamental problems in the market of tourist services are also solved in a unique way:

What and how the problem of production should be solved on the basis of effective use of limited resources, taking into account the needs of consumers;

Producers' activities should be organized on the basis of maximum use of resources, especially labor resources;

When answering the question of what kind of tourist product should be produced, the enterprise should follow the rule of avoiding loss and striving to make a profit. In this case, it is desirable that the distribution of income be fair, that is, they should not exceed the amount necessary to cover expenses and ensure the average profit of the industry. Therefore, it is appropriate to set a reasonable price for tourist products.

In order to achieve high results in the market of tourist services, it is necessary to fulfill all these conditions to the maximum. We believe that doing this without government support may not bring the expected results.

In order to determine the role and importance of state regulation in the operation and development of the tourist services market, "basic conditions - structure

We will study the "behavior-result" paradigm. Based on the developed law, we identify a number of variable factors and characteristics that affect the economic outcome of the tourist services market, and establish orderly connections and connections between them. A model describing these relationships is presented in Figure 1.

It can be seen that the positive economic results of the activity of the tourist services market are reflected in: an increase in the efficiency of development, the creation of new jobs, an increase in national income, an increase in the share of the tourism sector in the GNP, the full satisfaction of the population's demands for tourist products, the development of infrastructure, an increase in the standard of living of the population, etc.

In turn, the result of the activity of the tourist services market directly depends on the set of actions that determine the behavior of this market. The behavior of the market of tourist services is determined by the price policy of the organizations operating in this market, the choice of the name culture of the products they produce, the use of scientific and technical innovations during production activities, the implementation of innovative activities, the investment policy of tourist organizations, the conduct of marketing research, new types of the production of tourist products, as well as the use of new modern methods of advertising in the realization of tourist products, reflect a set of actions. Of course, this set of actions comes from the meaning and essence of the market.

In order to fully understand the content of the market, it is necessary to know its internal structure. The content of the market is reflected in its behavior, and its internal structure is reflected in its structure.

The structure of the tourist services market: the number of tour agents and tour operators who create and sell tourist products, the number of buyers of tourist products, the variety of tourist products, the variety of services provided to tourists during the tour, the number of counterparties operating in the market of tourist services, mutual integration of tourist organizations, tourism It consists of elements such as diversification of the activities of organizations. Of course, these elements are formed on the basis of supply and demand. On the other hand, the basic conditions existing in a certain area create demand and supply, respectively, and serve as the basis for the formation of the relevant market.

The existing tourism potential in the Republic of Uzbekistan served as the main basis for the formation of the national tourist services market.

Ideally, this tourist services market structure, which forms its behavior based on the market regulation mechanism, should automatically achieve high socio-economic results. As a result of various objective reasons, the market may become helpless in some cases and may not give the expected results. In this case, the state implements a policy of intervention in its economy. In doing so, the state can improve outcomes through its regulatory levers by appropriately influencing both fundamental conditions, market structure, and market behavior.

This situation is theoretically explained as follows: "Efficiency of the national economy is a multi-factor indicator, in which the achieved result of efficiency may largely depend on the role of the state or market system in the economy. Because much higher efficiency, firstly, through market regulation methods; secondly, by consciously centralized management of the economy

only from a single center; thirdly, it is achieved by combining state intervention and market methods in the reproduction process.

Figure 1: State regulation of the tourist services market

In the conditions of a market economy, the state regulation of the economy consists of a system of activities of a legislative, executive and control nature.

This system of activities constitutes state policy. The essence of the state regulation of the development of the tourist services market is reflected in the setting of specific goals aimed at the development of tourism before the relevant state bodies, the measures developed in this regard and the set of necessary tools for their implementation. It should be emphasized that in some countries, the state policy related to the tourism industry is carried out separately.

without going, it is carried out in integration with the state policy directed to other sectors of the economy. Of course, in this case, the way to achieve the goal of the state policy on the development of tourism is abstract and cannot give the expected results.

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